

Supplemental Table 1. List of altered genes reported in APT/PC excluding those that were reported only in hypermutator phenotype (acquired during TMZ treatment and not present in the primary untreated tumor). Genes are listed alphabetically.

Gene	Tumor type	Number of positive cases	Number of sequenced cases	References
<i>ATRX</i>	Corticotroph, Pit1-lineage	1 PC	1 PC	(1)
		4 APT + 4 PC	4 APT + 4 PC	(2)
		1 PC with <i>TP53</i> mutation	Case report	(3)
		2 APT with <i>TP53</i> mutations	18 PT with <i>USP8</i> wt	(4)
<i>CABLES1</i> *	Corticotroph	1 PT with aggressive features (our of 4 mutant PT)	181 PT tumors	(5)
<i>CDKN2A/B</i> *	Lactotroph	3 high-risk PT	38 high-risk PT	(6)
		1 PC	Case report	(7)
		1 PC	4 APT + 4 PC	(2)
		1 PC	2 PC (from 41 APT)	(8)
<i>CHEK2</i> *	Gonadotroph	1PC	Case report	(9)
<i>DAXX</i>	Corticotroph	2 PT with <i>TP53</i> mutations and aggressive behavior	18 PT with <i>USP8</i> wt	(4)
<i>GNAS</i> *	Somatotroph	1 APT	Case report	(10)
		1 APT	41 APT	(8)
<i>H-RAS</i>	Corticotroph, Lactotroph	1 ATP	19 PT	(11)
		3 metastases (absent in the primary PCs)	5 PC+ 6 recurrent, invasive PT	(12)
		6 invasive PT	91 invasive PT	(13)
<i>MEN1</i> *	All types	1 PC	Case report	(14)
		1 PC	Case report	(15)
		1 PC	Case report	(16)
		1 PC	Case report	(17)
		1 rapid-growing atypical PT	Case report	(18)
		1 PT with aggressive features	134 PT (14 defined as aggressive)	(19)
<i>MLH1</i> *#	Corticotroph	1 APT	Case report	(18)
		1 PC	Case report	(20)

The table continues on the next page.

PT, pituitary tumor; APT, aggressive PT, as defined by the ESE guidelines (40); PC, pituitary carcinoma.

* Mutations have been reported in non-APT as well.

In many cases mutations are detected after TMZ treatment (hypermutator phenotype).

Suppl. Table 1. Cont.

Gene	Tumor type	Number of positive cases	Number of sequenced cases	References
<i>MSH2</i> #	Corticotroph, lactotroph	1 PC	Case report, patients with Lynch syndrome (1PC with <i>MSH2</i> mutations and 2 non-APT with either <i>MSH6</i> or <i>PMS2</i> mutations)	(21)
		1APT	Case report	(22)
		1 APT	Case report	(23)
<i>MSH6</i> *#	Corticotroph, lactotroph	1 atypical PT with aggressive features	Case report	(24)
		1 PC	Case report	(21)
		1 rapid-growing atypical PT	Case report	(18)
<i>NF1</i> *	Corticotroph	1 PC	Case report	(25)
<i>NF2</i>	Lactotroph	1 APT	4 APT + 4 PC	(2)
<i>PIK3CA</i> *	All types	8 invasive PT	92 invasive PT	(13)
		3 invasive macroadenomas (our of 4 mutant PT)	33 sporadic PT	(26)
		1 APT	41 APT	(8)
<i>POU6F2</i>	Lactotroph	1 PT with aggressive features	Case report	(27)
<i>PTEN</i>	Corticotroph	1 PC	Case report	(3)
		1 PT with aggressive features	134 PT (14 defined as aggressive)	(19)
		1 APT+ 1 PC	4 APT + 4 PC	(2)
		1 metastasis (absent in the primary PC)	Case report	(25)
<i>RB1</i>	Lactotroph	1 likely aggressive PT	25 PT	(28)
		1 APT	4 APT + 4 PC	(2)
<i>SDHB</i> *	Somatotroph, gonadotroph	1 PT with aggressive features	Case report	(29)
		1 PC	Case report	(30)
<i>SF3B1</i> *	Lactotroph	5 PT with Knosp grade ≥ 3 and progression (among 45 <i>SF3B1</i> mutant)	227 PT (11 Knosp grade ≥ 3 with progression)	(31)
		1 PC	Case report	(7)

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In many cases mutations are detected after TMZ treatment (hypermutator phenotype).

Suppl. Table 1. Cont.

Gene	Tumor type	Number of positive cases	Number of sequenced cases	References
TP53	Corticotroph, Pit1-lineage	2 PC	14 PT (6 PC)	(32)
		1 APT	Case report	(33)
		1 APT (mutation possibly induced by radiation therapy)	Case report	(34)
		1 PC	Case report	(35)
		1 PC with ATRX mutations	Case report	(3)
		6 APT (2 with ATRX mutations and 2 with DAXX mutations)	18 PT with USP8 wt	(4)
		1 PT with aggressive features	134 PT (14 defined as aggressive)	(19)
		5 APT	22 PT with aggressive features	(36)
		4 APT + 2 PC with ATRX mutations	4 APT + 4 PC	(2)
		2 PC	Case report	(37)(25)
		1 APT	Case report	(20)
		9 APT	86 corticotroph PT (24 APT)	(38)
3 APT	41 APT	(8)		
USP8*	Corticotroph	3 APT + 1 PC	22 PT with aggressive features	(36)
		6 APT	24 APT	(38)
		1PC	10 corticotroph PT (2 likely APT, 1 PC)	(39)

PT, pituitary tumor; APT, aggressive PT, as defined by the ESE guidelines (40); PC, pituitary carcinoma.

* Mutations have been reported in non-APT as well

In many cases mutations are detected after TMZ treatment (hypermutator phenotype).

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